

Example Data Management Plan – complete version with full responses

Developmental predictors of anxiety in childhood and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on self-reported anxiety behaviours in young adults

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Complete version with full responses

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ELIXIR-UK

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Based on

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(Q1) Proposal name

Developmental predictors of anxiety in childhood and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on self-reported anxiety behaviours in young adults.

(Q2) Description of the data: Type of study

This study is a secondary analysis study using existing datasets from the Millennium Cohort Study (MCS) to examine whether indicators of childhood anxiety are predictive of (a) an individual's self-reported experience of the COVID-19 pandemic and (b) ongoing anxiety issues in adulthood.

(Q3) Description of the data: Types of data

This study will use existing datasets and resources from the MCS held by the UK Data Service. We will also generate documentation including protocols, reports, and statistical models.

(Q4) Description of the data: Origin of the data

This secondary analysis study will use existing data from the UK Data Service. We will examine Millennium Cohort Study (MCS) data – a longitudinal population study following approximately 19000 young people born across the UK from 2000-2002.

We will investigate data from the following sweeps: age 3 (2004), age 5 (2006), age 14 (2015), age 17 (2018) and age 23 (2023) in addition to data from a subset of participants and/or their parents responding to COVID-19-specific questionnaires (waves 1-3; 2020-2021).

(Q5) Description of the data: Format and scale of the data

Data and associated documentation will be downloaded from the UK Data Service as .tab and/or .sav files. Both file types can be opened and edited within SPSS statistical analyses software however .tab is an open, machine-readable format. The data will be comprised of analyses of questionnaire and interview records from approximately 12000 participants (combined self-reported and/or parent-reported). We estimate the total size of the data and associated documentation will not exceed 10 GB.

(Q6) Managing, storing and curating data

Data will be downloaded and stored on the University storage system. This is a secure, resilient, networked data storage system with multi-site backup. All data will be handled in line with the UK Data Service End User Licence Agreement, the UK Data Service Additional Conditions of Use and the University Research Data Management Policy. Given the publicly accessible nature of the dataset, no identifiable participant information is available to or accessed by the research team.

All data will be stored within a project folder containing sub-folders for each dataset and we will use a consistent and predefined file-naming strategy to label analyses within SPSS and to name all documentation associated with the project. Access to the folders containing the data will be limited to the applicant and named associate members of the research team.

(Q7) Metadata standards and data documentation

The original data is accompanied by rich metadata and documentation outlining the coding schemas used by the original researchers. Our analyses will utilise the same variable coding system to ensure consistency and ability to cross-reference with the original study. We will additionally include robust documentation describing our methodology, inclusion/exclusion criteria and methods of statistical analyses including scripts.

(Q8) Data preservation strategy and standards

We will preserve our analyses and associated documentation within the University Archive System. All files will be stored in standard, machine-readable formats to enable long-term preservation and the data will be curated as per the requirements of the University Archive. To comply with the BBSRC Data Sharing Policy we will retain the data for 10 years. The raw source data will be preserved long-term by the UK Data Service.

(Q9) Where will data be shared?

The source data is publicly available through the UK Data Service. We will share our methodology - including statistical models and associated scripts/macros - and results through publication(s) in an open-access journal(s). We will include a clear Data Availability Statement within all publications highlighting that additional data is freely available upon request to the corresponding author(s).

(Q10) When will data be available?

Our analyses and associated documentation will be available at the point of publication to enable maximal reuse by others. Source data is openly available from the UK Data Service. We will endeavour to respond to data access requests in a responsible and timely manner.

(Q11) How will data be made findable and accessible?

Summary data will be accessible through open-access publication which will include a Data Access statement. We will use persistent identifiers wherever possible to enhance findability. In addition, we will present our findings at local meetings as well as national and international conferences and we will engage with the University Press Office and the MCS founding researchers at UCL to create a press release if the findings are of significant public interest.

(Q12) How will data be made reusable?

We will generate comprehensive metadata to enhance data reusability. We will share all statistical model coding and macros with those who request access. The source MCS data is openly available to all.

(Q13) Restrictions or delays to sharing, with planned actions to limit such restrictions

We do not anticipate any delays to data sharing and will endeavour to share data access requests in a timely and responsible manner.

(Q14) Secondary use

We anticipate that our findings will be of interest to other researchers working in related field(s) both nationally and internationally. It may also be of interest to external stakeholders such as those working in child and adolescent mental health services, education and healthcare.

(Q15) Formal information/data security standards

None identified

(Q16) Main risks to data security

This study is a secondary analysis of a population cohort study. We will not hold any identifiable participant data and all research team members with access to the data will be bound by the UK Data Service End User Licence Agreement which prevents any attempts to identify individuals from the data. The pseudonymised data we will hold will be stored on the University's secure storage system which is accessed using University sign-in details. It is only accessible while on the University campus or via VPN which requires separate sign-in credentials.

(Q17) Capabilities

The University has a Research Data Management Policy and secure data storage infrastructure to allow efficient and optimised research data management. All costs for data storage and archiving have been included in this application and we do not anticipate incurring additional costs.

(Q18) Maintaining and implementing the Data Management Plan

This data management plan is a living document and will be reviewed every 6 months to ensure the project data management is on track and to revise if necessary.

(Q19) Environmental considerations

The University is a signatory of the Concordat for the Environmental Sustainability of Research and Innovation Practice and is committed to net zero by 2040 as part of the Climate Strategy. We will ensure all equipment such as laptops and printers are turned off and unplugged whenever possible and will join meetings such as conferences virtually wherever possible. We will additionally ensure that all members of the research group spend time on appropriate sustainability training and that they are recognised for implementing sustainable practices.

(Q20) Responsibilities

All members of the research team, including the group leader, are responsible for data management, maintaining appropriate documentation and quality assurance. Responsibility for data security lies with the group leader in addition to the University Information Services and Information Security divisions.